

1 SUPPORTING INFORMATION

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3 **Hybrid catalysts based on carbene anchored on**

4 **inorganic supports with hierarchical porosity**

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16 Fig.S1 - The XRD pattern of microporous HZSM-5 (a, black), HP HZSM-5 (b, red) and

17 NHC-HP HZSM-5 (c, blue).

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Fig.S2 - The XRD patterns of microporous SAPO-5 (a, black), HP SAPO-5 (b, red) and NHC-HP SAPO-5 (c, blue).

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Fig. S3: ^1H rotor-synchronized spin-echo NMR spectra of calcined HP-HZSM-5 (left panel) and calcined HP-SAPO-5 (right panel) recorded without (top) and with (middle) ^{27}Al irradiation. A MAS rate of 15 kHz and an echo delay of 2ms were employed during the experiments. The difference spectra (top-middle) is shown at the bottom.

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33 Fig. S4: ^{29}Si MAS (left panel) and ^{27}Al MAS (right panel) NMR spectra of NHC/HP-HZSM-
 34 5 (top) and HP-HZSM-5 (bottom). ^{29}Si MAS and ^{27}Al MAS NMR spectra were recorded
 35 using a MAS rate of 10 and 15 kHz, respectively, under proton decoupling conditions.

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39 Fig. S5: ^{29}Si (left panel), ^{27}Al (middle panel) and ^{31}P (right panel) MAS NMR spectra of
 40 NHC/HP-SAPO-5 (top) and HP-SAPO-5 (bottom). ^{29}Si , ^{27}Al and ^{31}P MAS NMR spectra
 41 were recorded using a MAS rate of 10 and 15 kHz, respectively, under proton decoupling
 42 conditions.

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